

ReNEW

D4.2 Overall Living Labs Implementation Plan and Management

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Acronyms and Abbreviations	Meaning
Acronym / Abbreviation	Meaning
4SHIP	4Shipping
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIS	Automatic Identification System
APA	Agência Portuguesa do Ambiente
APDL	Administração dos Portos do Douro, Leixões e Viana do Castelo, SA
CC	Command Centre
CCNR	Central Commission for the Navigation of the Rhine
CEMT	Confederation of European Maritime Technology Societies
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
CO2	Carbon Dioxide
DGRM	Directorate-General for Natural Resources, Safety and Maritime Services
DT	Digital Twin
FMP	Floating Modular Platform
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GPS	Global Positioning System
GRIWT	Green and Resilient Inland Waterway Transport
HPC	High Performance Computing
IMEC	Interuniversitair Micro-Electronica Centrum
ING	Internationale Nederlanden Groep
ITA	Instituto Tecnológico De Aragon
IW	Inland Waterway
IWT	Inland Waterway Transport
KNT	Konnecta
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LL	Living Lab
MAG	Magellan
MCC	Mobile Command Centre
NOx	Nitrogen Oxides
OHB	Opleidingscentrum Voor Hout En Bouw Vzw
PAN	Panteia
RIS	River Information Services
ROC	Remote Operation Centre
UGAL	Universitatea Dunarea De Jos Din Galati
VHF	Very High Frequency
VTS	Vessel Traffic Services
WP	Work Package
ZES	Zero Emission Services

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Executive Summary

The ReNEW project, continues to stay dedicated to fostering the transition to a smart, green, sustainable, and climate-resilient inland waterway transportation system. This deliverable presents the updated version of the implementation plan and management of the Living Labs within the ReNEW consortium. In response to the project's dynamic nature and commitment to continuous evolution, this updated version includes the task of Audits and Plan for Transferability, which addresses (a) the development of a framework with indicators and criteria to establish sustainability, replicability, and transferability actions, as well as (b) aligning Living Labs progress with capacity building, innovation management, and commercialization. A preliminary diagnosis of initial site conditions was performed during the first version of this deliverable to guide the evaluation, ensuring replicability of integrated solutions across demo sites. Throughout the process and timeline, the ReNEW approach is fully agile, allowing for continuous refinement of Living Labs functionalities via innovations in WP1, WP2, and WP3. The Living Labs' progress is now intricately connected to capacity building, with an emphasis on Innovation Management and commercialization alignment. This strategic shift is intended to improve the project's long-term viability, replication, and transferability. The initial site conditions diagnosis provided a foundational understanding for evaluating and replicating integrated solutions, reinforcing the ReNEW project's impact and potential for widespread adoption, which aligns with the project's overall vision of maximising stakeholder benefits from emerging technologies.

1 Introduction

1.1 High Level Implementation Plan towards Sustainability

This document lays out the progress carried out in each of the 4 ReNEW Living Labs (LL) till M18 of the project in order to achieve the common project objective as well as the LL-specific objectives while moving towards capacity building as well as monitoring the overall innovation development process from conceptualisation to commercialization within each Living Lab (LL). The structure of the document follows almost the same structure of the previous document with a few additions.

Following the LL specific multidisciplinary approach already described during the initial version of the deliverable the objective is to align Living Labs progress towards capacity building, Innovation Management and commercialisation by analysing, synthesizing, and creating connections between many disciplines so to establish sustainability replicability and transferability of the project and its' results. Moreover, following an iterative approach introduced in version 1 of this document it is ensured that the overall planning and development process is under constant refinement and improvement thus adhering to the agile concept of operations of the project. Monthly meetings and cross WP interactions between various LL stakeholder and LL leaders as well as partners with technical expertise act as a key factor in advancing and refining the overall LLs progress towards the project's goals.

1.2 Mapping the ReNEW Output

The purpose of this section is to map ReNEW's GA commitments, both within the formal Deliverables as well as the Task description, against the project's respective outputs and work performed.

Table 1. Adherence to ReNEW's GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

Deliverable D4.2 Overall Living Labs Implementation Plan and Management
Auditing & Monitoring Report and assessment.
Task T4.1 Overall Living Labs Implementation Plan and Management
Task 4.1 comprises planning & baselining imperatives to establish the overall implementation plan, including key activities per quarter and overseeing project milestones along with key actors and necessary prerequisites. Central to this step is initiating the evaluation of the project's LLs, including information on the baseline conditions, relevant assumptions to be considered, high level information flows, checklists, and templates, including templates and structure for LL presentations and their associated Deliverables. Associated KPIs and key roles and interactions are clearly defined within this process.

ReNEW GA Element Title	ReNEW GA Element Outline	Respective Chapter (s) and Document Description
ST4.1.1 Living Labs Implementation Plan	Develop the LL implementation plan for adopted scenarios (technologies, resilience and sustainability innovations, digitisation, models and simulation, and decision supported strategies) that (a) integrate innovations and ReNEW initiatives engaging all relevant stakeholders (b) define the integration needs for the operations processes including the Data Space and Digital Twins (c) design the specific elements and connections (d) develop tools for optimal configuration of all components. Once the plan is structured, and prior to Living Labs implementation, it will be presented to the executive board and the Living Labs stakeholders and validated with them in order to ensure its feasibility, and to achieve buy-in and consensus from all partners and maximise its efficiency.	The objectives of this subtask was covered in the previous version of this deliverable D4.1
ST4.1.2 Audits and Plan for Transferability	(a) Prepare framework of indicators and criteria so to establish sustainability and replicability and transferability actions, (b) Align Living Labs progress towards capacity building, innovation management and commercialisation. Perform a starting diagnosis, in order to determine the initial site conditions. This would also be important for the evaluation, as well as for the replicability of the project about, the integrated solutions installed and tested at the demo sites.	This subtask and its relevant objectives will be covered within this deliverable that will act as a revised version of this document with additional content as depicted in this subtask.
ST4.1.3 Living Labs Implementation Monitoring, Validation and Lessons Learned	Perform LL monitoring (a) Implement and deploy a monitoring system, (b) develop the executive plans following all previous constraints (c) identify possible limitations of the technologies and innovations to optimize their performances, (d) monitor compliance with existing National and European regulations and policies. Perform LL Validation and Assessment (a) Validate the achievements of the Living Labs with respect to the fulfilment of the objectives of ReNEW (b) assess the performance (c) validate on-site and via simulated use cases the measures of the LL scenarios (d) Perform comparative assessment of the living lab before and after the implemented initiatives (e) Develop outlines for standardisation and replicability and produce the lessons learnt and transferability of strategies and resulting outputs.	This subtask and its relevant objectives will be covered in D4.3, a revised version of this document with additional content as depicted in this subtask.

2 The Living Labs Implementation Plan

2.1 ReNEW implementation Plan Objectives

Following the initial approach for the implementation plan task 4.1 plays an important role in shaping the Living Labs implementation plan within the ReNEW project, integrating resilience and sustainability solutions from WP1 to WP3 and correlating these solutions with the objectives of WP5 to upscale the results into a commercial path. Moreover, the plan through the LLs aims at highlighting innovations within the Inland Waterways transportation system while strengthening capacity building as described on deliverables D5.2 and D5.3. The process begins with a thorough needs assessment, identifying key stakeholders and their requirements. A stakeholder engagement plan is crafted to ensure continuous involvement and feedback. Integration needs for operations processes, including Data Space and Digital Twins, were defined, followed by the detailed design phase, specifying technologies, components, and connections. The plan incorporates monitoring and reporting mechanisms, defining key performance indicators (KPIs) and data collection methods for the lifecycle of the project. In terms of post-validation through the executive board and LL stakeholders, the plan has entered the initial construction phase.

2.2 The ReNEW Implementation Plan Methodology

As a whole the ReNEW project employs an agile approach in executing its implementation plan, aligning activities with developments in WP1 to WP3 for resilience and sustainability provisions. As already described in D4.1 a blend of SCRUM and KANBAN methodologies are being used, while the agile framework emphasizes on continuous delivery and improvement by managing work in progress and optimizing workflow efficiency. Reporting phases are split into two main cycles at M18 and M36, with intermediate milestones aligning with the project's plan and implementation objectives.

The Living Labs (LL) implementation plan (T4.1) is rooted in the Living Labs mechanism, integrating innovations from WP1, WP2, and WP3 into LLs (LL1, LL2, LL3, and LL4). As previously mentioned regular Scrum meetings facilitate progress review, obstacle discussion, and future planning, ensuring focus and tracking for ReNEW Living Labs teams. The incorporation of Scrum concepts, such as Backlog, Sprint, Sprint Master, Delivery Owner, and Sprint Review, enhances efficiency and responsiveness throughout the LL implementation process while providing a seamless integration between LLs and the technical WPs(1,2,3) and fulfilling the goals of WP5 towards commercialisation and capacity building by aligning their progress in the right path.

2.3 The ReNEW Implementation Plan Timeline

The overall Living Labs implementation plan of WP4 starts with T4.1. The first cycle as described on the agile approach ended in M18, and below the progress of the LLs so far is presented. Finally, the last version of this deliverable that will attempt to present the overall process followed and the results that were produced during the whole period of the project is at M34 (D4.3).

The agile process, as outlined in D4.1 and further elaborated below, guides the entire timeline leading to the culmination of Living Labs (LLs) progress and their final outcomes. This comprehensive approach ensures that the development and achievements of each LL are closely monitored through corresponding deliverables, providing a transparent and accountable framework for the project's evolution. Based on the aforementioned timeline, and starting with M19 the second cycle of the design and planning of the LLs will be initiated.

Implementation Plan Development. (M1-M3)

Develop the LL implementation plan and conduct a needs assessment. Define the technologies, resilience and sustainability innovations, digitisation, models and simulation, and decision-supported strategies that will be adopted. Engage relevant stakeholders and identify integration needs for operations processes, including the Data Space and Digital Twins. Develop tools for optimal configuration of all components.

ReNEW Sprint (1-3, Monthly): Develop the plan, create a backlog of tasks for each. Present the plan to the executive board and stakeholders, collect feedback, and make necessary changes.

Kanban: Refine and update the backlog as needed, update the plan and backlog as needed based on stakeholder's feedback.

Design and plan the Living Lab specific tasks. (M4-M6)

Perform detailed LL design and planning, stakeholder's engagement, licensing and permitting for buildings and operation of the technologies, and iterative detailed LL solutions deployment.

ReNEW Sprint (4-6, Monthly): Plan and design detailed LL solutions in the Living Lab context.

Kanban: Monitor progress, prioritize tasks, and adjust as necessary.

Execute LL construction plan. (M6-M18)

Customize and configure technology, resilience and sustainability use cases, Data Spaces and Digital Twins, simulation, and monitoring solutions. Execute LL construction plan in a progressive and iterative mode.

ReNEW Sprint (6-18, Monthly): Execute the LL construction plan, customize and configure technology, and deploy solutions in iterative mode.

Kanban: Monitor progress, prioritize tasks, and adjust as necessary.

Monitor the Living Lab operations. (M10-M18)

Perform risk management and mitigation and take corrective actions as necessary. Collect data for KPIs and reporting.

Conduct a review of the Living Labs' progress and make necessary adjustments to the LL implementation plan based on the review.

ReNEW Sprint (10-18, Monthly): Perform monitoring, risk management, and mitigation, collect data for KPIs and reporting.

Kanban: Monitor progress, prioritize tasks, and adjust as necessary.

Create the second cycle of LL implementation plan. (M19-M20)

Based on the adjusted implementation plan. Design and plan the second cycle of Living Labs.

ReNEW Sprint: Develop the plan of the second implementation cycle, create a backlog of tasks for each. Present the plan to the executive board and stakeholders, collect feedback, and make necessary changes.

Kanban (19-20, Monthly): Refine and update the backlog as needed, update the plan and backlog as needed based on stakeholder's feedback.

Execute the second cycle of LL construction (M19-M33)

Customize and configure technology, resilience and sustainability use cases, Data Spaces and Digital Twins, simulation, and monitoring solutions.

ReNEW Sprint (19-33, Monthly): Execute the LL construction plan of the second cycle, customize and configure technology, and deploy solutions in iterative mode.

Kanban: Monitor progress, prioritize tasks, and adjust as necessary.

Monitor the second cycle of Living Lab operations. (M19-M33)

Perform risk management and mitigation and take corrective actions as necessary. Collect data for KPIs and reporting.

Conduct a review of the second cycle of Living Labs' progress and make necessary adjustments to the LL implementation plan based on the review.

ReNEW Sprint (19-33, Monthly): Perform monitoring, risk management, and mitigation, collect data for KPIs and reporting.

Kanban: Monitor progress, prioritize tasks, and adjust as necessary.

Living Labs Implementation Assessment. (M28-M34)

Execute the final cycle of LL implementation. Gather the results of the Living Labs operations and take any final corrective actions as necessary. Collect final data for KPIs and reporting.

Based on the above-described steps, shows the overall agile implementation plan per Living Lab. The detailed activities for each Living Lab depend on the specific LL requirements and will be captured in the LL backlog.

3 LL1 - Ghent's Multifunctional Synchronomodality City Logistics Hub

3.1 Context, Vision and Challenges of LL1

Aligning with the ReNEW project in terms of resilience and sustainability Living Lab 1 (LL1) in Ghent emerges as a testing ground, delving into the impact of climate changes and fostering innovative solutions for inland waterways transport (IWT). According to studies 2023 marked an unprecedented global temperature rise, becoming the warmest year on record. The Copernicus Climate Change Service reported a 1.48 degrees Celsius increase compared to pre-industrial levels. Europe, including Belgium, experienced significant climate anomalies in 2023. The region faced extreme events such as flooding, wildfires, drought, and heatwaves. The impacts were diverse, affecting human health, ecosystems, nature, and infrastructure. In Ghent, the city's water management strategies proved effective, emphasizing the importance of climate-resilient urban planning. Ghent's intricate water management system, featuring lock complexes and flood protection infrastructure, demonstrated its efficacy in maintaining stable water levels. The city's commitment to increasing the "sponge effect" by creating extra space for water reflects a proactive approach to climate change. Ghent's three water basins, regulated by seven lock complexes, exemplify a successful strategy to safeguard against floods and fluctuations.

Aligned with the city's vision, LL1 in Ghent focuses on economic applications of water-related transport. The integration of green technologies, autonomy, and advanced infrastructure is pivotal. The goals include synchronizing cargo arrival via barges with multiple transport modes, testing syncro-modality solutions, and enhancing energy resilience with innovative power solutions like floating batteries. The aim is to align LL1 objectives with the broader vision of Ghent's city planners and water authorities. Fitting the Ghent logistics hub into the city's vision posed challenges, emphasizing the need for integration of emerging green technologies. The introduction of autonomous low or zero-emission barges, floating platforms, diverse transportation means for cargo and people during disasters, and a modular shore module are identified as key solutions. These innovations aim to enhance autonomy, maneuverability, platooning capabilities, and emergency power supply. LL1's results contribute to the overarching impact objectives of the ReNEW project. By sharing LL objectives with other cities, the knowledge gained in Ghent aims to influence and optimize inland waterways usage on a broader scale.

In summary, LL1 in Ghent serves as a pivotal testing ground where the city's vision, climate challenges, and innovative solutions intersect. The collaborative efforts within this living lab contribute to the development of resilient and sustainable practices for inland waterways transport, setting a precedent for future urban planning in the face of climate change.

3.2 Infrastructure & Tools Progress

3.2.1 Digital Infrastructure

Within the Living Lab framework, significant strides have been made in enhancing the digital infrastructure to support autonomous shipping operations. Presently, one urban vessel operated by OHB operates remotely through SEAFAR, marking a milestone in autonomous maritime endeavors. The vessel seamlessly communicates critical information to the Shore Control Centre in Antwerp through SEAFAR, underlining the robustness of the established digital connections.

The utilization of AIS (Automatic Identification System) has been pivotal in precisely locating the ship, providing real-time insights into its movements. Considering advancements, an evaluation for the integration of em-trak AIS transceivers is underway. These cutting-edge transceivers are renowned for their superior performance, reliability, and connectivity, aligning perfectly with the evolving digital infrastructure needs. The deployment of LiDAR cameras and existing sensors on the remote-controlled ship underscores the commitment to leveraging sensor technologies for comprehensive data collection. Recognizing the evolving nature of autonomous shipping requirements, plans are underway to augment the sensor suite based on insights outlined in D4.1 & D4.6. Exploring the potential of a 5G private network represents a significant leap in digital infrastructure development. Collaborating with Proximus, research is ongoing to implement a private 5G network, offering enhanced control over network access. Anticipated tests with this cutting-edge network at the end of 2024 are poised to validate its efficacy in securely and efficiently commanding ships and drones from a shore-based control center. Finally, Work Package 3 of the ReNEW project is advancing the development of the initial digital twin demonstrator. This tool assesses waterway navigability and monitors sustainability and resilience KPIs for different transport modes. Incorporating user stories aligned with Living Lab 1 (LL1) requirements, the demonstrator compares the navigability of the Flexible Modular Platform and Smart Ship in the Ghent area. As it matures, the demonstrator will include more scenarios and parameters for comprehensive assessments. To achieve situational awareness in the multimodal city logistics hub, real-time data from physical assets (smart ship, loading systems, drone, environmental alert system, floating energy system) is digitally connected to the ReNEW Data Space. This ensures the Digital Twin remains accurate and supports informed decision-making. This ongoing progress highlights the commitment to enhancing the ReNEW project's overall capabilities. In essence, the Living Lab's digital infrastructure progress is of utmost importance to embracing technological advancements, ensuring the reliability, safety, and effectiveness of autonomous shipping operations in the evolving maritime landscape.

3.2.2 Physical Infrastructure

The development of the Smart Terminal within Living Lab 1 represents a transformative ecosystem designed for resilience and autonomy. Comprising terrain, ships, loading/unloading infrastructure, and storage options, this modular system ensures operational continuity, even in the absence of on-site staff. The terminal incorporates functionalities like remote-controlled sailing, autonomous mooring, and crane-assisted loading/unloading, offering a glimpse into the future of efficient and self-sustaining terminal operations. The designated test base, situated in the North Sea Port near the Westbeeksluis, underwent meticulous planning. Conducted in four phases, the site survey ensured optimal use of its elongated shape, providing 400 meters of quay for concurrent ship mooring. Strategically located near arterial roads and waterway connections, the site promises seamless access for inland and city transport. With the aid of architectural planning to maximize loading efficiency, allowing trucks to enter on one side and exit on the other. Reinforced concrete slabs, each measuring 15m x 15m, facilitate loading/unloading activities through a robust 100-ton crane. The careful consideration of terrain layout and excavation ensures the practicality and effectiveness of the Smart Terminal's physical infrastructure. In parallel, the existing infrastructure of LL1 for remote-controlled shipping is evolving. OHB's ownership of two urban barges, with one under construction, aligns with the vision of autonomous waterborne transport. The onshore command center by SEAFAR, operational in Ghent, collaborates with local logistics providers to complement the on-water operations. In parallel testing and validation are paramount in this phase for object recognition hardware and cameras that are tested for reliability and security. Various types of cameras, specifically tailored for waterborne object recognition, have been rigorously tested in collaboration with research institutions while SEAFAR plans to deploy their camera set on the new vessel, marking a pivotal step in enhancing the vision systems of autonomous shipping. Looking forward, the focus is on the remote control capability of the urban boat from SEAFAR's shore control center in Antwerp. Technical installations in the control center establish a robust connection with on-board equipment through PLC, enabling data reception and remote control. The above information highlight the progress being done in the context of LL1. More information and details can be found also in D4.7 that present a more complete depiction of the developments of each use case of LL1.

3.3 Data Collection

In a complex environment such of LL1, the diverse use cases demand a comprehensive array of data to drive informed decision-making and ensure the successful implementation of various projects. To begin with, environmental Data stands out the most, gathered through strategically placed sensors in the seaport and canal areas of Ghent and Zelzate. This data takes center stage, directly contributing to the demanding concepts of resilience and sustainability within the Living Lab objectives. Moreover, ship availability and location data emerge as critical components for the seamless execution of use cases. The Automatic Identification System (AIS) serves as a reliable source, offering real-time insights into ship movements, thereby facilitating effective planning and coordination. Crucial for scenarios involving cranes, data on their location and operation are indispensable. The application of track and trace devices to cranes provides valuable information on their whereabouts, whether on

land or onboard a ship, ensuring optimal operational efficiency. Furthermore, floating battery data requirements align with those of the associated ship, emphasizing the importance of tracking the location and status of floating batteries. This ensures a comprehensive understanding of their role within specific use cases. In terms of Energy Management System (EMS) providing insights into battery system status, the EMS becomes instrumental in managing these systems, particularly regarding charging capacity. This data optimization contributes to the reliability and efficiency of the Living Lab infrastructure. As Living Lab 1 initiatives progress, ongoing efforts in data collection mechanisms fortify the Lab's capacity to generate meaningful insights. The convergence of these diverse data sets navigates the complexities of use cases, playing an important role in the overall success of the LL1.

3.4 KPIs

Previously described in D4.1 the KPIs in the framework of the Ghent LL, are presented also in detail below. LL1 focuses mainly on the 5 horizontal KPIs set within the project thus adhering to the concept of ReNEW itself.

Ensure Navigability for Inland Waterways:

The primary objective is to assure navigability even during extreme weather events, and the KPI sets a target of achieving 80% capacity during disruptive scenarios. To realize this, an application scenario will be developed in collaboration with ITA, focusing on simulations and strategies to address challenges posed by extreme weather conditions.

Enhance Land/Sea/Infrastructure Resilience:

This objective revolves around enhancing resilience to both extreme weather and human-induced events, with a KPI demanding a minimum of 80% capacity at the network level during disruptions. The approach involves improving the resilience of land and sea infrastructure, particularly managing the human factor in driving automated systems to ensure robust network-level capacity during disruptive events.

Increase Modal Shift:

The goal is to achieve a 20% increase in modal shift, primarily through effective tests and stakeholder meetings. The KPI entails the successful execution of trials and engagements, optimizing transshipment processes and fostering a sustainable shift in transportation modes.

Ensure Resilience and Functionality of Passenger and Freight Transport:

This objective emphasizes the need to ensure the resilience and smooth functioning of both passenger and freight transport. The associated KPI focuses on establishing robust cooperation between regulatory authorities, water authorities, and urban logistics stakeholders. Successful

implementation involves fostering collaboration among regulatory bodies responsible for loading/unloading points, water authorities maintaining waterways, and stakeholders ensuring an ample supply of goods and people within the urban area.

Reduce Environmental Impact (CO₂ and NO_x):

The objective here is to minimize the environmental impact, specifically targeting a 90% reduction in CO₂ and NO_x emissions. The KPI is centered around achieving this significant reduction. The implementation strategy involves incorporating electric propulsion with e-engines and battery packs in urban vessels, with the ultimate aim of achieving a 100% reduction in emissions compared to internal combustion engines.

3.5 Consortium Stakeholders and their Role

As already mentioned in D4.1 the internal and external stakeholders and their role within LL1 remain as is. However, some additions were made in order to assist with the complete implementation of the LL1 and its extensive use cases. Thus, the team of Akkodis will help with the development of the drone system on the rescue vessel, that will help to map the environment of the disaster area and pass on data to the CC of any victims while Sintef Ocean will provide advice on development of a remote controlled or automated mooring system, based on their experience on conducting feasibility studies on similar systems for ferries and short sea ships. Last but not least, ICCS with extensive experience in state-of-the-art in-situ sensors measuring the water level and quality. The implementation of synergistic framework allowing the combination of in-situ data with satellite altimetry data is important in estimating the deployment of rescue equipment and people in the affected area.

3.6 Conclusions and Outcomes

Living Lab 1 within the ReNEW project, serves as a dynamic research and innovation laboratory with real-life applications, dedicated to proving resilience and sustainability in Inland Waterways Transport (IWT). The collaborative effort invested in the design of the new urban vessel encapsulates various essential elements, reflecting a comprehensive approach to innovation. The study of the existing small urban vessel paved the way for the creation of a simulation model by partner UGAL. Computer models were employed to study the behaviour of the smaller vessel in shallow water, providing critical insights for design adjustments. Exploration of the impact of wind, currents, ebb and flow, and waves in an area with multiple rivers influenced the final vessel design. An in-depth examination of various drivetrains for ships, including inboard and outboard engines, informed the selection process. Moreover, extensive research determined the necessary functionalities for the "Smart Terminal" to ensure flexibility and resilience, encompassing features like loading ramps, drones, and remote

control equipment. Multiple scenarios were analyzed for the installation of a crane onboard, leading to recommendations based on cargo weight considerations and workload safety. The ship's design was adjusted accordingly, opting for the ro-ro mobile crane model. The culmination of data and analyses resulted in the creation of a new, adapted ship design, setting the stage for further development. Material acquisitions, including aluminum plates and engines, were successfully completed in M18. With the design finalized to meet intended applications, the construction phase commenced with the welding of the hull and installation of engines. The upcoming months will witness the implementation of the remaining applications and use cases outlined in the project. Barring unexpected circumstances, and moving according to plan, the construction is anticipated to be completed, encompassing the installation of propulsion and steering elements. Subsequent phases will involve an extensive testing period, covering various elements such as the ship's behavior in shallow water and strong currents, remote-controlled sailing from the command center in Antwerp, and the testing of Smart Terminal components, including drones and remote-controlled cranes. The comprehensive efforts and advancements made in LL1 underscore its significance in paving the way for innovative solutions in the realm of inland waterways transport, contributing to the overarching goals of resilience and sustainability in the ReNEW project.

4 LL2 - DOURO River Waterway

4.1 Context, Vision and Challenges of LL2

The Douro Living Lab represents an innovative initiative poised to tackle the multifaceted challenges posed by extreme weather events and illegal wastewater dumping in the Douro region. Comprising of two distinct use cases, the project sets out to significantly elevate the resilience, safety, and environmental sustainability of inland waterways. Use Case 1 takes a pioneering approach by developing a digital twin to accurately predict the performance of ships navigating the intricate Douro River. Leveraging real-time data from already installed as well as new meteorological and hydrological sensors, this use case aims to enhance emergency planning, optimize navigation efficiency, and ensure the safety of passengers.

In parallel, Use Case 2 is dedicated to the prevention of illegal wastewater dumping in the Douro River through the implementation of real-time monitoring, smart contracts, and blockchain technology. This transformative endeavor seeks to instill a heightened sense of ecological responsibility among vessel operators, ultimately safeguarding water quality and preserving the delicate local ecosystem. The Douro Living Lab, through these innovative use cases, integrates real-time data analysis, digital twin technology, predictive models, smart contracts, and blockchain to offer tangible solutions for safer navigation and environmental protection. The methodology employed for the Douro Living Lab embarks on a structured and iterative journey to realize the ambitious objectives of Use Case 1 and Use Case 2. This comprehensive methodology encompasses pivotal elements such as stakeholder engagement, a data-driven approach utilizing advanced technologies, and the meticulous development of a digital twin. With the integration of rule-based logic for enforcement, dataspace for effective data management, and a continuous improvement process, the methodology ensures a holistic and evolving strategy. The incorporation of a timeline-driven approach further guarantees timely evaluations, culminating in the achievement of Living Lab objectives. In essence, this agile methodology not only facilitates collaboration but also underscores the significance of data-driven decision-making and technology integration.

4.2 Infrastructure & Tools Progress

4.2.1 Digital Infrastructure

As described in D4.1 the Douro LL is already using several digital tools in order to monitor the river in near real time and collect readings from the various sensors already installed. The information system is publicly available in APDL's River Information Services Portal also enriched with AIS and RIS data providing valuable information for the river, the current weather conditions and forecast as well as the vessels navigating through the river. Following the progress of the LL for use case 1 the main efforts of the last months were focused on the development of a virtual model of the Douro River that

is able to simulate the river's behaviour during extreme events. The model will provide the possibility to explore several what-if scenarios and better understand the river's flow. In order to achieve the aforementioned task, the partners involved are dedicated in developing a digital twin simulation with predictive capabilities thus upscaling emergency planning. Currently, the focus of the solution lies within the integration of hydrological model predictions into the digital twin that is being developed. In the upcoming period the aim is to transform the information system into a decision support system making it an innovative river management system. For use case 2 the research is still ongoing in terms of the blockchain solution. Although the architecture is designed and described as well in D4.10 the main deployment for the blockchain is still ongoing. An extensive timeplan is also presented in detail in D4.10.

4.2.2 Physical Infrastructure

Regarding the status of the physical infrastructure of the Douro LL as already described for use case 1 they are equipped with several water level and water velocity sensors as well as weather stations across the river. is already equipped with thirty water level gauges across the river as well as six meteorological stations and four surface water velocity sensors. Worthy of notice is the fact that a majority of vessels are already equipped with GPS devices, enabling the continuous broadcasting of each vessel's precise position. Highlighting the progress of the LL it is deemed necessary to procure more of the same sensors in order to produce more accurate data and results. In terms of use case 2 and since the ships already have sensors to monitor certain parameters onboard there will be no need to do retrofitting for the installation of additional sensors. The only infrastructure that will be necessary is a small, rugged computer/laptop with 4G/5G connectivity to process the information from the ship's sensors and upload it to the blockchain.

4.3 Data Collection

Regarding data collection, and while having significant data already collected from the preinstalled sensors, an enhancement in the data collection systems is expected facilitating the seamless integration of real-time data sourced from the new meteorological and hydrological sensors. This refined data collection is pivotal for gaining a more precise and holistic insight into the river's dynamics and environmental conditions. Additionally, the plan involves the creation of an advanced digital twin that will engage with a hydrodynamic model through data spaces and LDES. This advancement signifies a substantial leap forward in terms of capacity to faithfully replicate and comprehend the intricacies of the Douro River, particularly during extreme conditions.

4.4 KPIs

Aside from the horizontal KPIs set within ReNEW for the LLs each LL has several other key performance indicators that play a pivotal role in assessing the effectiveness of both Use Case 1 and Use Case 2 within the Douro Living Lab, providing robust metrics for their evaluation.

For Use Case 1, two KPIs have been established to gauge its impact on navigability during extreme weather events and the resilience of the river's infrastructure in the face of significant disruptions.

Navigability During Extreme Weather Events is the first KPI, focusing on evaluating the Douro River's ability to facilitate safe and efficient inland navigation during major floods, flash floods, or droughts. This KPI is essential for quantifying the river's capacity to maintain navigable conditions under challenging circumstances. The assessment utilizes real-time data from meteorological and hydrological sensors, AIS, RIS, water level gauges, and weather forecasts, offering insights into river water levels, velocities, weather conditions, and vessel movements. The method involves calculating the percentage of navigable capacity during extreme weather events by comparing actual vessel movements to predetermined navigation plans and locking schedules. The target is to ensure a minimum of 50% navigability capacity during such events, promoting safer navigation and minimizing disruptions.

The second KPI, Infrastructure Resilience During Extreme Disruptions, focuses on evaluating the effectiveness of the Douro River's infrastructure, encompassing locks, canals, and inter-modality platforms, amid significant weather challenges. Data required for this KPI includes real-time updates on the status of infrastructure components, covering water levels, equipment status, damages, or malfunctions. The measurement method assesses the percentage of infrastructure components functioning as expected during disruptions, monitoring the response time and effectiveness of emergency measures for damage control and functionality restoration. The target is to maintain at least 80% infrastructure resilience at the network level during extreme disruptions, ensuring a substantial portion of the river's infrastructure remains operational under severe weather conditions.

In the context of Use Case 2, a distinct KPI, Compliance with Wastewater Monitoring, is outlined to evaluate adherence to proposed wastewater monitoring practices on a voluntary basis. The necessary data involves conducting a survey among Douro inland waterway ship owners and operators, outlining the proposed monitoring mechanism and soliciting their willingness to volunteer their ships for a trial run of the technology. The measurement method calculates the percentage of vessels available to participate in the pilot, serving as a reference to the entire fleet currently navigating the Douro. The target is to receive positive feedback from at least 5% of the current fleet, indicating proactive engagement in the wastewater monitoring initiative.

4.5 Consortium Stakeholders and their Role

The relevant internal and external stakeholders within LL2 remain as is

4.6 Conclusions and Outcomes

In conclusion, the successful implementation of both use cases is paramount to the Douro Living Lab's mission. These innovative solutions, combining advanced technologies and strategic methodologies that are being developed are poised to set new benchmarks in the management and conservation of waterways. By aligning with the comprehensive goals of the ReNEW project, the Douro Living Lab emerges as a beacon for promoting sustainability, resilience, and technological innovation in the realm of inland water systems. The collaborative efforts and outcomes achieved through these use cases mark a significant step toward realizing a future of smart, green, and resilient inland waterways, benefiting not only the Douro region but also serving as a model for sustainable practices globally.

5 LL3 - Planning mitigation for climate resilient and sustainable transport infrastructure boosting modal shift

5.1 Context, Vision and Challenges of LL3

Living Lab 3 aims to respond to stringent emission reduction objectives, and since governments are actively advocating for a modal shift to reduce traffic congestion, inland waterways emerge as a greener alternative to road transport yet face reliability challenges. Current limitations in accessing real-time information on water levels, forecasts, and obstacles hinder effective inland waterways route planning. The lack of seamless integration of this critical information with existing route-planning software poses a substantial challenge. As previously mentioned in D4.1 the main challenges to be addressed are the reliability issues that encompass disruptions at terminals, extreme weather conditions, and disruptions in the supply chain. Users lack timely information, hindering proactive decision-making during the planning process. The East and South Corridor of inland waterways in The Netherlands, encompassing the Rhombus concept, is particularly affected. The Rhombus, connecting major waterways, faces disruptions that impact the entire inland waterway system. The recent Seine Scheldt connection addition improves connectivity but emphasizes the need for resilience. Heading towards a solution LL3 by leveraging the existing "Blue Wave" platform is developing add-on modules to enhance resilience and sustainability, while aligning with the ReNEW project's objectives. More specifically, "Blue Wave" is a comprehensive solution that promotes safety and efficient shipping by offering real-time insights to various stakeholders in the logistics chain. In that context LL3 is actively empowering the platform through the integration of a Planning and Mitigation Module. In order to reach this goal LL3 and the partners involved harness historical data on past disruptions and mitigation strategies, in order for the module to establish a knowledge base for effective problem-solving in specific conditions and locations. The platform's scope extends across waterways in multiple countries, providing dynamic insights into traffic, mooring occupancy, and lock waiting times. Following that effort the new modules become instrumental in seamlessly integrating planning services with real-time disruption information.

5.2 Infrastructure & Tools Progress

5.2.1 Digital Infrastructure

Regarding the progress and advancements of the digital infrastructure and tools for LL3, the Routeplanner is the main focus with three integral modules designed to enhance navigation, efficiency, and adaptability. The Maintenance Module serves as a crucial component, identifies ongoing maintenance works, monitors fairway conditions, tracks fuel prices, and provides critical information on tides and water levels across the EU network. Serving as an information hub, this module ensures stakeholders are well-informed about the dynamic aspects of waterway navigation.

Employing Dijkstra's algorithm, the Helpers Submodule efficiently calculate optimal routes within the provided output path. By factoring in delays from Fairway Traffic Management (FTM) messages, operational schedules of locks and bridges, and specific time allocations, this submodule ensures that the calculated routes are not only efficient but also aligned with real-time conditions. The Runtime Road and Rail Route Planner, employs the A* algorithm to determine the most efficient path between points A and B via rail and road. This module, integrated with an open-Route Service API, calculates associated costs, fuel consumption, and CO2 emissions, prioritizing both cost-efficiency and environmental impact. The dynamic Planning Mitigation Module adds a layer of real-time adaptability, enabling users to plan inland waterway transport, request timeslots, and receive updates from skippers. It integrates seamlessly with the Routeplanner and features a sophisticated mitigation strategies advice algorithm based on historical disruption data. A testing phase has been initiated for the Planning Mitigation Module v1.0, ensuring its effectiveness in addressing disruptions and delays. This progress underscores LL3's commitment to leveraging cutting-edge digital tools, including the Blue Wave platform, to optimize inland waterway transportation, encourage modal shifts, and enhance the overall resilience of the waterway system. The integration of advanced modules and continuous testing reflects the evolution and refinement of the digital infrastructure supporting LL3's goals for sustainability and efficiency in inland waterway logistics while it is noteworthy to report that Over the next year, extending until Q2 2025, the focus will be on the finalization and testing of the routeplanner and the planning mitigation module, engaging with feedback from at least 100 skippers. Moving into the latter half of 2024, the plan involves seamlessly integrating LL3 services with the components and solutions from ReNEW Work Package 3, a matter that is currently under research in terms of development and integration. The general idea behind this is that the LL3-developed application, along with the terminal module and routeplanner, will integrate with the dataspace to effortlessly exchange data, obtaining real-time weather updates and conditions, such as those provided by EURIS. Additionally, LL3 applications will utilize simulation models functioning as a digital twin. These simulations will be instrumental in informing the planning module, aiding in the creation of more advanced, efficient, and resilient planning solutions.

5.2.2 Physical Infrastructure

In the context of LL3's digital-centric approach to project objectives, the physical infrastructure was deliberately optimized through the strategic placement of various sensors, both within vessels and across the designated study area. Sensors inside inland waterway vessels, including emission detectors, depth measurement tools, GPS systems, and fuel consumption monitors, form a critical network capturing essential data on vessel performance and environmental impact. Complementing this, environmental sensors strategically positioned in the study area focus on parameters like water levels, velocity, and weather conditions, providing real-time insights crucial for safe navigation.

5.3 Data Collection

In the past six months, LL3 has been dedicated to enhancing its data collection processes, focusing on the practical aspects of information gathering to bolster operational efficiency. The inland water vessels in LL3 are now equipped with a variety of sensors, capturing real-time data on engine performance, fuel consumption, loading status, navigation details, and location. This sensor-generated dataset provides valuable insights into the day-to-day operations of the vessels, contributing to a comprehensive understanding of their functionality. Additionally, LL3 has established connections with external data sources, incorporating weather-related data, EURIS information, and AIS data for actively operating vessels. These efforts aim to enrich the dataset with environmental and operational parameters.

The development of the inland shipping network within the route planner is another noteworthy achievement for LL3's data collection process. Utilizing national sources like VisuRIS and Waterway Characteristics in the Netherlands, the network's physical attributes, including waterway dimensions, current directions, and sailing profiles, have been systematically mapped. Dynamic elements such as water levels and the availability of waterways and structures are regularly updated from several sources. This integration of data empowers LL3 with a real-time understanding of the dynamic conditions of waterways, providing essential insights for effective route planning and decision-making within the context of LL3. Moreover, as previously mentioned another set of data input is planned to be used in the form of simulation models under a digital twins concept stored within the dataspace being developed in WP3.

5.4 KPIs

In addition to the horizontal Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) established within the ReNEW project, LL3 recognizes the significance of specific KPIs tailored to assess the effectiveness of LL3 and the innovative solutions it incorporates. To align with the overarching project KPIs, LL3 will meticulously calculate and evaluate the following key metrics.

Market Share of Inland Waterways (IWW):

The objective is to evaluate the modal shift influenced by LL3's route planner, measuring the transition toward environmentally friendly modes of transport. The calculation will utilize actual market shares available in 2023 from the Dutch Bureau of Statistics.

Reliability Enhancement:

LL3's route planner aims to enhance IWW reliability through real-time weather and terminal information, suggesting optimal routes for on-time arrivals. Evaluation metrics include the percentage of trips arriving at terminals without delays on an annual basis, the number of delayed services per year, and the total delay hours per vessel type per year. Data sources for these metrics include vessel sensors and terminal data.

Environmental Indicators:

The objective is to assess environmental impact considering factors such as distance traveled, vessel speed, and load factor. Evaluation metrics encompass energy consumption per vessel category per year and total greenhouse gas emissions (kg CO₂e) per vessel category per year, derived from energy consumption.

Efficiency Indicators:

The objective is to evaluate LL3's route planner's impact on operational efficiency in IWW services. Evaluation metrics include vessel capacity utilization (% of capacity used per vessel type per year) based on vessel weight data and average vessel speed per vessel category (km/h per trip), gathered from onboard sensors.

Resilience in Disruptions:

The objective is to mitigate disruptions in IWW transport using LL3's route planner. Evaluation metrics include the number of disruptions reported in the route planner per year and the number of redirected services due to disruptions using the route planner per year.

By complying with the aforementioned KPIs a step forward is made for assessing LL3's impact on the inland waterways and thus providing a comprehensive framework to measure the success and effectiveness of the innovative solutions implemented in LL3.

5.5 Consortium Stakeholders and their Role

The relevant internal and external stakeholders within LL3 remain as is

5.6 Conclusions and Outcomes

In conclusion, the progress made within LL3 over the past months underscores a significant stride towards achieving the objectives set forth in the ReNEW project. The integration of diverse data sources, including sensor-generated insights from inland water vessels and external datasets such as weather information, EURIS, and AIS data, has fortified LL3's foundation for data-driven decision-making while highlighting the importance of the application's modularity and use. Also the mapping of the inland shipping network within the route planner, utilizing national sources for physical attributes and dynamic elements, signifies a robust framework for navigating waterways efficiently.

Moreover, the development and testing of the Planning Mitigation Module, alongside the Routeplanner, exemplify LL3's commitment to enhancing user capabilities in planning and responding to disruptions in real-time. The incorporation of alternative route options further amplifies user flexibility, allowing them to tailor their choices based on diverse criteria and scenarios. Finally the integration with the ReNEW WP3 components holds promise for even more innovative planning solutions.

6 LL4 - Autonomous Zero Emission Barge

6.1 Context, Vision and Challenges of LL4

As already discussed it is of utmost importance to highlight that Inland waterway transport is grappling with formidable challenges, presenting opportunities for innovation, particularly in response to environmental adversities like low water levels due to climate change. Living Lab 4 (LL4) emerges as a strategic response, envisioning a future of sustainable transport on European inland waterways through the design and demonstration of a series of revolutionary zero-emission commercial vessels.

The prevailing fleet's average age, often reliant on combustion engines, underscores environmental concerns. Recognizing the unsustainability of merely upgrading existing vessels, LL4's vision is to showcase the resilience of zero-emission transport for containers through commercial vessels on inland waterways. This innovative approach aims not merely at a singular vessel but at transforming the entire fleet, with the success of this demonstration laying the foundation for a future fleet of identical zero-emission vessels.

Investing in green technology necessitates a paradigm shift in vessel design principles, and the X-Barge, a product of LL4, embodies this innovation. Completed in January 2024, the X-Barge is a modular, fully automated, and zero-emission vessel, designed to navigate challenges posed by climate change, scarcity of crew, and emissions. The vessel's unique design, featuring containerized batteries in power packs, ensures flexibility and contingency. It leverages a series of modular ships, allowing for the integration of alternative energy sources as they become commercially viable.

A crucial aspect of the X-Barge is its unmanned design, achieved by relocating crew operations from the ship to the shore. This not only enhances energy efficiency but also addresses the industry's pressing issue – a shortage of qualified crew. By removing the wheelhouse and accommodation, the X-Barge optimizes energy usage, contributing to the vessel's competitiveness in price with traditional ships. The savings generated from this approach are redirected into green technology, positioning the X-Barge as a trailblazer in environmentally conscious inland waterway transport.

The relocation of crew to the shore aims to counteract potential delays in goods delivery, preventing a modal shift from waterway to road transport. The X-Barge, designed to be a CEMT Class IV vessel, prioritizes future-proofing, ensuring navigability even in low water levels—a critical consideration given the escalating impacts of climate change.

To achieve the ambitious goals of LL4, a comprehensive strategy is outlined. Real-world testing and analysis of the X-Barge focus on operational and financial viability under diverse climatological conditions. Acquisition of necessary permits for autonomous operation involves discussions with waterway and port authorities to validate safety and compliance. Infrastructure adaptations at terminals are made to facilitate autonomous operations, including mooring, loading, unloading, and battery charging. Initiatives are undertaken to raise awareness and foster social acceptance of

autonomous inland barges, addressing crew shortages and supporting the transition to green energy. The commencement of actual commercial container flows demonstrates the practicality and efficiency of Class 4 inland barges with autonomous capabilities and alternative propulsion methods.

In navigating these challenges, LL4 aspires to lead a transformative shift in inland waterway transport, aligning with sustainability goals and showcasing the X-Barge as a beacon of innovation for the industry. All the above advancements can be highlighted below in terms of the progress of LL4.

6.2 Infrastructure & Tools Progress

6.2.1 Digital Infrastructure

As previously mentioned in D4.1 a comprehensive 4G/5G network is in place across all waterways, facilitating seamless data flows and enabling remote control and operation of the X-Barge. Moreover, several redundant systems will be used such as WiFi and satellite coverage that act as a failsafe to the main networks. These advancements aim to enhance the efficiency and capabilities of the vessel.

Furthermore, the X-Barge will play a crucial role as a testbed for innovations emerging from within ReNEW. Running simulations and implementing the latest technologies on the X-Barge will serve as a practical application and validation ground for the digital tools and AI algorithms developed within the project. This approach ensures that the vessel not only benefits from cutting-edge innovations but actively contributes to the refinement and validation of emerging technologies, creating a symbiotic relationship between the X-Barge project and the broader goals of ReNEW.

6.2.2 Physical Infrastructure

The X-Barge has achieved significant milestones in its technical development, with the completion of the ship's design in January 2024. The vessel is envisioned as a series of modular ships employing containerized batteries within power packs. The initial vessel in the series will serve as a demonstration for Living Lab 4. The modularity of the design allows for flexibility, accommodating different energy sources in power packs with a standardized interface once commercially viable. This feature provides contingency options, including the potential use of a stage 5 diesel generator in the power packs temporarily, ensuring electrical energy for the ship in case of insufficient charging options along routes in 2025.

The X-Barge stands out as a fully zero-emission electrical ship, eliminating internal combustion engines and fossil fuels from its system—a pivotal distinction from conventional ships. The ship systems are highly automated to optimize operational efficiency and reduce energy demand. This level of automation also facilitates remote control and monitoring of ship systems, surpassing current industry best practices. Power packs, housed in standard 20-foot containers, serve as independent

power sources, not integrated into the ship. This design ensures the ship's future-proof nature, allowing easy adaptation to more efficient green energy sources as they become commercially available. Power packs can be charged on land and swapped with depleted packs on the ship or charged on the ship while docked. This design choice enhances operational flexibility and adaptability to evolving energy technologies. Model tests at the Flanders Hydraulics laboratory aim to reduce the ship's energy needs in shallow and confined waters, ensure maneuverability, and generate input parameters for the maneuvering system. The X-Barge is classified as a CEMT Class IV vessel, chosen for its future-proof characteristics, not only in energy usage but also concerning climate change and navigability in low water levels.

Operationally, the X-Barge focuses on energy efficiency, cost-effectiveness, and simplified work processes. The three on-board power packs with batteries offer a range of 250 km, and ongoing discussions with ports aim to establish swap locations for batteries. The ship's operational planning is optimized for efficient battery swapping, and personnel involved are trained in the safe handling of electrical installations and batteries. Maintenance of propulsion systems is simplified, eliminating the need for dry dock facilities.

6.3 Data Collection

To ensure the autonomous X-Barge operates efficiently and undergoes proper loading/unloading, various data sources are essential. These include location data, energy requirements, external conditions affecting navigation (wind, draft, currents), cargo details, and handling information. All operational data for the vessel will be acquired through sensors.

With the X-Barge design finalized, a comprehensive study has been initiated to determine the most suitable vessel design, emphasizing hydrodynamic efficiency, propulsion and resistance, and optimal loading. This involves conducting physical tests using a scale model of the vessel in a towing tank at the Flanders Hydraulic Institute. Additionally, numerical simulations utilizing Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) codes will be employed. Data gathered from both experimental and numerical approaches will be cross-referenced for validation and verification purposes.

Information pertaining to fairway infrastructure, such as bridge opening times and lock statuses, is accessible through relevant Inland Waterway (IW) authorities. The operation center manages the data flows and remotely oversees the vessel's navigation during its journeys. The completion of the X-Barge design ensures a comprehensive approach to data acquisition and testing for its efficient and autonomous operation.

6.4 KPIs

Outlined in the Grant Agreement for LL4 are three key performance indicators (KPIs) that serve as pivotal benchmarks for the project's success. These KPIs include providing evidence of a 5-20% increase in modal shift to Inland Water Transport (IWT), demonstrating zero emissions, and showcasing a reduced environmental impact concerning emissions as well as soil and water pollution. The focal point of utilizing the X-Barge within this context is to showcase a substantial improvement in navigability capacity ranging between 30-50%, accompanied by a targeted increase in modal shift by 20%. This emphasis on modal shift is crucial for mitigating congestion issues. However, the paramount achievement lies in the profound reduction of the environmental footprint, manifesting as a 100% reduction in CO2 emissions and alleviating concerns related to noise pollution, as well as minimizing adverse effects on riverbanks and the associated flora and fauna.

To effectively measure and evaluate these KPIs, a comprehensive table has been provided, detailing the specific metrics and methodologies involved in assessing the success of the X-Barge project. The integrated data from this table includes economic performance and competitiveness, emissions (GHG), and the effect on riverbanks and waterway habitats. Additionally, energy needs under different water depths will be scrutinized to ensure a comprehensive understanding of the project's environmental impact. The dynamic nature of the Class 4 inland barges necessitates ongoing testing and analysis to gauge their performance concerning environmental conditions and social acceptance. Additionally, the acquisition of necessary permits from relevant authorities plays a crucial role in navigating the regulatory landscape. The innovative approach of crewless operation coupled with alternative propulsion methods positions the X-Barges to be economically competitive, facilitating a substantial reduction in CO2 emissions. This shift towards an environmentally friendly mode of transport is anticipated to contribute significantly to reducing road congestion through an increased modal shift to inland water transport.

6.5 Consortium Stakeholders and their Role

The relevant internal and external stakeholders within LL4 remain as is since the design phase of the X-Barge is completed.

6.6 Conclusions and Outcomes

Concluding with LL4, it is safe to assume it has achieved significant milestones, with completed tasks and ongoing initiatives showcasing notable progress. The design phase for the X-Barge is now complete, marking the readiness to initiate hull construction. Upcoming discussions with the system integrator in the following months are crucial for ensuring the

seamless functionality of the X-Barge. Comprehensive engagement with relevant authorities has been undertaken, with an official application for testing in the dedicated area already submitted. Furthermore, essential contracts with a shipping line and potential shippers have been successfully concluded. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) have been defined to assess the X-Barge's performance under diverse climatological conditions, including low water levels and adverse weather, with a particular focus on evaluating its impact on climate through factors such as emission reductions (CO₂, NO_x) and modal shift.

7 Conclusions

Concluding, the Living Labs within the ReNEW project highlight progress, innovation, and collaborative dedication. Each Living Lab, tailored to its specific regional dynamics, demonstrates significant advancements in promoting resilience and sustainability in inland waterways transport (IWT). The unique contexts of the four LLs collectively contribute to the overarching objectives of the ReNEW project.

The strides achieved in digital infrastructure, the strategic use of smart sensors, and the integration of autonomous technologies showcase a united move toward the future of IWT. Stakeholder engagement, a shared focus in all 4 of them, underscores the necessity of collaborative efforts for successful implementation. The consistent emphasis on key performance indicators (KPIs) in all Living Labs signifies a dedication to achieving measurable outcomes that directly contribute to the goals of the ReNEW project.

A common theme across the Living Labs is the commitment to capacity building and innovation. From developing digital twins to incorporating sustainable urban planning, the Living Labs embody a holistic and evolving strategy. The integration of diverse expertise, technological advancements, and sustainable practices places the Living Labs at the forefront of reshaping a resilient and sustainable future for inland waterways.

As the Living Labs progress, they offer valuable insights and solutions capable of redefining water systems management. Through a steadfast commitment to cutting-edge technologies and collaborative endeavors, the Living Labs serve as guiding lights, paving the way for a new era in IWT. The witnessed progress not only reflects the success of the Living Labs but also underscores their broader impact on the future landscape of water transport systems.

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